

Optimised community model code options tested on selected cases

Deliverable D2.2

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme
under Grant Agreement No 675191

About this document

Work package in charge: WP2 Scalability

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 31 August 2018

Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

Lead author:

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC): Kim Serradell

Other contributing authors:

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ): Philipp Neumann, Panagiotis Adamidis

European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF): Peter Dueben, Peter Bauer

Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) Foundation: Silvia Mocavero, Sandro Fiore, Giovanni Aloisio

BULL SAS (BULL): Harald Braun

Contacts: esiwace@dkrz.de

Visit us on: www.esiwace.eu

Follow us on Twitter: [@esiwace](https://twitter.com/esiwace)

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the authors view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of contents

1. Abstract /publishable summary	4
2. Conclusion & Results	4
3. Project objectives	4
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	5
5. References (<i>Bibliography</i>)	5
6. Dissemination and uptake	6
6.1 Dissemination	6
7. The delivery is delayed: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	6
8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	6
9. Sustainability	6
9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date.....	6
9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	6
10. Dissemination activities	7

1. Abstract /publishable summary

In this deliverable, we document some use cases in different community model codes, i.e. OpenIFS and NEMO (being part of EC-Earth) as well as ICON, describing some results including performance improvements. The document will be split in different sections for IFS/NEMO/EC-Earth and ICON.

2. Conclusion & Results

Source code optimisations and related performance gains are the main results of this deliverable. For the IFS, two different approaches using different technologies have been tested to overlap computation and communication.

Regarding the NEMO ocean model, three main optimisations have been accomplished: improving domain decomposition, finding and optimising communications in some hot spots of the model and developing a hybrid parallelisation scheme.

In the EC-Earth coupled climate model, a detailed analysis in the coupling strategy led to important performance improvements, reducing the time devoted to coupling.

Finally for ICON, developments to improve the asynchronous I/O are presented.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user	No

community.	
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

Partners can be easily identified by the case reported. See attached document on the different optimisations.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- M.C. Acosta, X. Yepes-Arbós, S. Valcke, E. Maisonnave, K. Serradell, O. Mula-Valls, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2016). Performance analysis of EC-Earth 3.2: Coupling. BSC-CES Technical Memorandum 2016-006
- Epicoco, S. Mocavero, A.R. Porter, S.M. Pickles, M. Ashworth, G. Aloisio (2017). Hybridisation strategies and data structures for the NEMO ocean model. International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342016684930>.
- O. Tintó Prims, M. Castrillo, M.C. Acosta, O. Mula-Valls, A. Sanchez Lorente, K. Serradell, A. Cortés, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2018). Finding, analysing and solving MPI communication bottlenecks in Earth System models. Journal of Computational Science, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2018.04.015>.
- O. Tintó, M. Acosta, M. Castrillo, A. Cortés, A. Sanchez, K. Serradell, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2017). Optimizing domain decomposition in an ocean model: the case of NEMO, Procedia Computer Science 108:776-785, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.05.257>.

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Material detailed in this deliverable has been discussed in 4 publications, see Section 5.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The material has further been shared with HPC and weather/climate audiences in the scope of conferences and workshops, including ISC HPC and ENES HPC workshops.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

In the Description of the Action, this deliverable was indicated as OTHER for the category “type”. Although the actual output of this work is the improved source code, we provide in the following a short document to outline our accomplishments.

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Several optimisations could push community models significantly forward in collaborative efforts of model developers and experts from HPC industry.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

Links have been built with WP3 on the use of Arm tools.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a conference	Philipp Neumann (DKRZ) et al., Talk at EGU 2018 “Performance predictions for storm-resolving simulations of the climate system”	8-13 April 2018, Vienna (AT)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.egu2018.eu/ and https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	80
Participation to a conference	Philipp Neumann (DKRZ) et al., Talk at ESCO 2018 “Performance predictions for storm-resolving simulations of the climate system”	3-8 June 2018, Pilsen (CZ)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	http://www.esco2018.femhub.com/ and https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	50
Participation to a workshop	Philipp Neumann (DKRZ) et al., “The ESIWACE demonstrators: Scalability, performance prediction, evaluation” at the 5th ENES HPC Workshop	17-18 May 2018, Lecce (IT)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop	50
Participation to a	Philipp Neumann	24-28 June 2018,	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	40

conference	(DKRZ) et al., “Towards global cloud- resolving weather and climate prediction at exascale” at ISC HPC 2018	Frankfurt (DE)	(higher education, Research)		
Participation to a conference	K. Serradell (BSC) et al., “EC-Earth, a coupled Climate Model for extreme Event Prediction” at ISC HPC 2018	24-28 June 2018, Frankfurt (DE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	40
Participation to a workshop	Kim Serradell (BSC) presentation at the EC-Earth meeting	29-31 May 2017, Helsinki (FI)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/ec-earth-meeting-may-2017-helsinki and https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	50
Participation to a workshop	M. Acosta (BSC) et al. “HPC for high-resolution climate and weather modelling” at the 5th ENES HPC Workshop	17-18 May 2018, Lecce (IT)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop and https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	50
Participation to a workshop	M. Castrillo (BSC) et al. “JLESC Performance activities in Earth Science Department” at Joint Laboratory Initiative (JLESC)	17 April 2018, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	120

Participation to a workshop	M. Castrillo (BSC) et al. "Optimización de modelos de Ciencias de la Tierra" at the Workshop at the Spanish HPC network meeting (RES)	28-29 September 2017, Santiago de Compostela (ES)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://www.res.es/en/events/11th-res-users-meeting-hpc-advisory-council-conference and https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace/	48
Participation to a workshop	S. Mocavero (CMCC) Talk on "Towards KNL: the NEMO ocean model case study", at the KNL Workshop	22-23 March 2017, Bologna (IT)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1346352	40

Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Not applicable.

Optimised community model code options tested on selected cases

Kim Serradell (BSC)
Peter Bauer (ECMWF)
Peter Dueben (ECMWF)
Silvia Mocavero (CMCC)
Sandro Fiore (CMCC)
Giovanni Aloisio (CMCC)
Philipp Neumann (DKRZ)

Introduction

In the framework of the ESIWACE WP2 on Scalability, partners have been working on analysing and improving models. Different approaches and techniques have been applied to improve performance in different machines and architectures. In the following document, we will show some optimisation examples in different uses.

The report is divided into sections for each main model used in the project.

Community models

IFS

Assessment of different programming models for overlapping computations and communication

Initial work: CRESTA

This work was originally initiated in a European Commission funded project on Collaborative Research into Exascale Systemware, Tools and Applications (CRESTA¹). The aim of CRESTA was to investigate efficiency gains obtainable from overlapping computations and communication in those parts of the IFS that are most communication intensive, namely the semi-Lagrangian (SL) advection scheme and the spectral transforms (ST). These model parts also constitute weather and climate dwarfs in the ESCAPE² project.

More specifically, the work focused on overlapping Legendre transforms with the associated transpositions, overlapping Fourier transforms with the associated transpositions, reworking the SL communications, substantially reducing communicated halo data and overlapping halo communications with SL interpolations. The CRESTA work was based on using Fortran2008 co-arrays (CAF; supported by Cray compilers) within the context of OpenMP parallel regions. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the operations related to SL advection and ST per time step in the IFS. Figure 2 shows the performance gains achieved on HECToR³ and TITAN⁴ Cray machines with standard MPI and CAF implementations, respectively. The results indicate a significant improvement of strong scalability reaching an approximate factor of 2 on HECToR and 1.5 on TITAN. The TITAN runs were also the largest core/node allocations ever used for the IFS at the time and greatly helped to understand the limits of scalability of the code.

¹ <https://www.epcc.ed.ac.uk/projects-portfolio/cresta-collaborative-research-exascale-systemware-tools-and-applications> (EU Seventh Framework Programme (ICT-2011.9.13); G. Mozdzyński, M. Hamrud, N.P. Wedi (2015), A Partitioned Global Address Space implementation of the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts Integrated Forecasting System, Int. J. High Perform. Comput. Appl., 29(3), 261.

² Energy-efficient Scalable Algorithms for Weather Prediction at Exascale; www.hpc-escape.eu.

³ <http://www.hector.ac.uk/>

⁴ <https://www.olcf.ornl.gov/olcf-resources/compute-systems/titan/>

Figure 1: Operations performed each time step in the IFS in either spectral or grid-point space. The dotted squares indicate operations that were optimised in CRESTA and ESIWACE.

Figure 2: Strong scaling behaviour of the IFS run (in throughput of forecast days per wall-clock day) at a global resolution of 10 km and 137 vertical levels on HECToR and TITAN in the CRESTA project. Control run on HECToR (green), run with co-arrays on HECToR (light blue), Control run on TITAN (dark blue) and with co-arrays for linear (red) and cubic (violet) grids.

Extension to GPI-2: ESIWACE

In ESIWACE, this study was extended to employing GPI-2⁵ one-sided communication – applied in the same model areas as Fortran 2008 co-arrays, but using a more portable run-time library interface. GPI-2 implements the GASPI⁶ specification, which is an API that originates from GPI. GPI-2 is an API for asynchronous communication that provides a flexible, scalable and fault tolerant interface for parallel applications. Further, the evaluation was extended to the latest model version of the IFS and run on the HPC system available at ECMWF (Cray XC-40).

Tasks x threads	Nodes	Experiments	Forecast days/day	Option
2160Tx12t	360	MPI	1104.9	-cc numa_node
2160Tx12t	360	MPI	1116.1	-cc cpu
2160Tx12t	360	CAF	815.6	-cc numa_node
2160Tx12t	360	CAF	846.0	-cc cpu
2160Tx12t	360	GPI-2	788.9	-cc numa_node

Table 1: Examples of IFS throughput performance for a 360-node allocation on the Cray XC-40 HPC with MPI, CAF and GPI-2, also enabling fast memory access when the CPU can access its local memory (-cc numa_node) vs standard (-cc cpu).

The results for a single allocation of 360 nodes are shown in Tab. 1 for all options using 2160 tasks and 12 threads per task. In contrast to the results of CRESTA, the MPI implementation performs best and outperforms CAF by about 25% and GPI-2 by about 30%. It was noted that the CAF SYNC has stability issues when the number of electrical groups is greater than one with the Aries interconnect. This was not an issue on TITAN with AMD Interlagos processors and the Gemini interconnect in 2014-15. An electrical group on the Cray XC-40 comprises 352 compute nodes. The GPI2 implementation did not encounter this problem yet uses an identical compute-communication overlap scheme.

From this evaluation the following conclusions were derived:

- The Cray XC-40 Aries switch is much faster, and the IFS cubic grid requires relatively less communication going from grid-point to spectral space. Hence, there is no overall performance benefit for the IFS to use CAF or GPI-2 over the default MPI implementation.
- One-sided communication is good for code areas in which computation and communication can be done asynchronously.
- Both CAF (language syntax) and GPI-2 (library interface) can equally be used to reduce wall time provided there is sufficient overlap while MPI one-sided communication performs poorly.

⁵ <http://www.gpi-site.com/>

⁶ <http://www.gaspi.de>

- Future MPI standard will adopt GPI-2-type like technology for one-sided communications.
- The Cray Titan CAF performance was primarily good because the Gemini switch on that system was relatively slow.
- CAF suffers from a lack of full implementations by manufacturers, but portability is crucial for any application. Cray is still the only vendor to provide a full CAF implementation. The Intel CAF implementation is incomplete as it cannot use OpenMP if using co-array features because co-array transfers are mapped to MPI, and MPI cannot be used in OpenMP parallel loops. However, even the Cray CAF implementation suffers from occasional failures.

This research is very relevant to understand these issues as future architectures are suspected to be more compute than communication capable. But both CAF and GPI-2 are non-trivial to program even for developers proficient with the MPI standard. This may be acceptable for short code sections that are expensive and have potential for compute/communication overlap. This could potentially be hidden within a domain-specific language environment that is being explored within ESCAPE and ESCAPE-2.

NEMO

Optimising domain decomposition in an ocean model: the case of NEMO

The Exclude Land Processes in NEMO is a tool to find proper namelist parameters for the ocean subdomain distribution by excluding land-only processes (NEMO allocates processors for land cells and then discards computations).

This tool has been developed and tested for NEMO first and then added to EC-Earth. A [paper](#) has been published and the code is available in a [git repository](#) at BSC.

The work done to integrate this tool into the EC-Earth model is described in a development portal [wikipage](#) (login needed).

Finding, analysing and solving MPI communication bottleneck

Detailed analysis of communication pattern

In this work, the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO), the state-of-the-art European global ocean circulation model, has been used as an example for analysing and solving a MPI communication problem. In the analysis exercise, it is shown how to answer the questions of where, why and what is degrading model's scalability, and how this information can help developers in finding solutions that will mitigate their eventual issues. This work also demonstrates how performance analysis carried out with small size experiments, using limited resources, can lead to optimisations that will impact bigger experiments running on thousands of cores, making it easier to deal with the exascale challenge.

A [paper](#) has been published and the code modifications have been integrated in the NEMO3.6 version of the code.

Integrated and simplified analysis tool

The detailed analysis described in the previous paragraph clearly shows that the cost of MPI communications is the most important factor of scalability limitation of the NEMO model. Any further scalability improvement in this model requires to carefully identify the place of the most costly MPI exchanges in the code and to characterise their function and the reason of their use, before being able to propose the next strategy of reduction or removal.

In NEMO-3.6, MPI communications are wrapped in a small number of high level routines co-located in a single FORTRAN file (`lib_mpp.F90`). This code structure strongly facilitates a quick and non-intrusive instrumentation for a study dedicated to the MPI communication structure. Basically, the NEMO communication library provides functionalities for horizontal halo exchange and global averages between horizontal subdomains. The second functionality is of less importance and out of the scope of the present study, considering that it is not used in the time stepping loop or can be disengaged in production mode. Every halo exchange of any variable of the code necessarily needs to be done through the generic “ROUTINE_LNK”. With a very light code change focused on this position, it is possible to identify and characterise the whole MPI communication pattern for further modifications. This instrumentation does not replace existing external solutions like “*extrae-paraver*” described in (Prims et al., 2018). The amount of information collected by our solution is much smaller, but it is able to deliver synthetic information for any kind of machine without any external library, without additional computing cost or additional post-processing.

Because of some initial assumptions of the existing internal timing library routine (`timing.F90`), we preferred not to modify and re-use its functionalities, but to slightly instrument the ROUTINE_LNK generic interface with MPI_Wtime calls. Following the strategy already deployed to estimate the coupled system load imbalance (Maisonave and Caubel, 2014⁷), a counter of the time spent in MPI routines, also called “waiting time”, is incremented in every call of a MPI send or receive operation. Symmetrically, a second counter is filled outside these two kinds of operation. Only two pieces of information per core are collected on two real scalar variables: the cumulated time spent to send/receive or (mostly) wait MPI messages and the complementary period of other operations (named “calculations”). This information is flushed at the simulation end by every MPI process standard output, without extra computation cost.

The strategic position of our measurements is the perfect place to not only estimate time spent on the communication routines but also to identify their calling routines and the size and kind (2D/3D or pointers of 3D arrays) of exchanged halo arrays. A normal counting is performed during the first and second time step of the simulation. The second time step is used to establish the sequence and the size of the exchanges. In the third time step, it is possible to substitute the model operations (step routine) by MPI exchanges of the realistic sequence of halo communications. This skeleton of realistic exchanges is useful to avoid processing the whole simulation and help to save computation resources during tests, as recently experienced by (Zheng and Marguinaud, 2018)⁸. In our case, the skeleton can be automatically set up for any NEMO configuration (resolution, namelist, CPP keys) during the first two time steps and applied during the rest of the simulation. We online produce (i) a full list of the calling routines that allows to identify the most communication demanding

⁷ E. Maisonave, A. Caubel, 2014, LUCIA, load balancing tool for OASIS coupled systems, Technical Report, TR/CMGC/14/63, SUC au CERFACS, URA CERFACS/CNRS No1875, France

⁸ Y. Zheng and P. Marguinaud, 2018, Simulation of the performance and scalability of message passing interface (MPI) communications of atmospheric models running on exascale supercomputers, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 11, 3409-3426, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-3409-2018>

routines of the various NEMO configurations and (ii) a separated counting, per time step, of halo exchanges for 2D/3D and simple/multiple arrays. Similarly, the sequence of the communications can be modified or the communication block can be even switched off on purpose to estimate the effect of such modification to the model performance.

As a first step, we focused our study on the “blue” part of the NEMO framework (ocean physics and dynamics), excluding sea-ice and I/O, modules that can be isolated and whose performances can be investigated separately. In addition, to be able to modulate the communication pattern or even switch off communications without causing instability failures, we weakly force at its boundaries a simplified rectangular pool. However, the rectangular boundaries can be connected with the same symmetry rules as any global grids (ORCA), which ensures realistic communication in addition to computational patterns. This new simplified NEMO configuration is called “BENCH”.

Applying our measurement tool to this simplified configuration, a better picture of scalability variations with resolution or machine is now available and it is even possible to clarify their origin. On our current supercomputers, a normal usage of resources limits scalability investigations to 1 or 0.25 degrees configurations. As shown in Figure 3, left, “waiting time” (MPI communications + calculation load imbalance, pink line) is the limiting factor for BENCH-1 speed (1 degree resolution, BENCH configuration, red line). The scalability limit is reached when the length of the MPI subdomain sides falls below 10x10 grid points. In addition, the difference between the fastest and the slowest calculations between MPI processes (orange line) gives an idea of the total calculation spread, i.e. load imbalance, between subdomains. Its contribution to the total waiting time is significant.

Figure 3, right, illustrates the imbalance of calculation time between the MPI processes. Processes of the last two nodes show extra calculations (array copies) of polar folding. They are the origin of most of the total imbalance as plotted in Figure3, left (orange line). Additional analysis (not shown) revealed that it is also at the origin of most of the extra waiting time. These analyses led to prioritise our current model performance enhancement work on polar folding effect reduction (on-going).

Figure 3, left: total time to solution, given in seconds per simulated year, of a BENCH-1degree horizontal resolution model, for several side lengths of MPI subdomains. The red line shows the total time to solution, the pink line shows the time spent to wait for halo arrays (MPI messages), the orange line shows the difference between slowest and fastest total calculations (excluding waiting time, see Figure 3, right) among MPI processes. Figure 3, right: total time to solution, but

excluding time spent to wait halo arrays, for each MPI process, same unit, same model configuration as in the left figure. The six measures are done with six different domain decompositions (domain side length in legend).

We also took benefit of the possibility to easily modulate the amount of communication to sharply estimate the MPI exchange effect on scalability. Figure 4 compares time to solution and calculation spread of our reference experiment with two others. In the first one, all halo exchanges were switched off. In the second one, exchanges were performed every two time steps only.

Figure 4, left: total time to solution and calculation spread, same experiment as Figure 3, left (red and pink lines). In a second experiment, communications are switched off. Total time to solution of this second experiment is shown in dark blue, with corresponding calculation spread in light blue. Figure 4, right: in a third experiment, realistic communications are performed every two time steps only. Total time to solution of this experiment in shown in dark green, with corresponding waiting time in light green.

The first experiment quantifies the dominant effect of communication on performances at every position of the scalability curve. As far as our measurement can be led, the remaining load imbalance cannot limit the scalability. The second experiment estimates the maximum benefit of a possible implementation of a communication-reduced algorithm such as the so-called double halo (a two point wide halo is transmitted every two time steps). Concluding, a non-intrusive instrumentation of our code brought information about MPI communication cost and structure. It helps us to identify the most appropriate incremental developments that our model needs to enhance its scalability.

First optimisations on BENCH configuration

Bull has been and is actively working on NEMO in collaboration with CNRS-IPSL and the NEMO HPC working group, especially on the following points:

- MPI optimisation on BENCH 1 (see presentation of BENCH 1 configuration from CNRS-IPSL)
 - Overlapping communications (loop splitting to improve non-blocking communication schemes)

- Performance improvement on the communication side at the cost of non-vectorised loop part (global effect is worst or equal).
- MPI Datatype to avoid user packing/unpacking and let the library to handle this part. Two MPI data types are tested: subarray and vector.
 - Both suffered from non-optimised libraries (Intel) on a small subdomain, but we envisioned better results on bigger subdomains
- Array initialisation optimisation ($a(:, :, :) = 0$ replaced by $a(:, :, jpk) = 0$)
 - Current results show a 40% gain in the nonosc function
- Kernel optimisations: Replacing “sign” by “if”
 - Current results show 9% of total gain (with the array initialisation optimisation)

All contributions will be delivered in a dedicated branch of the NEMO CNRS-IPSL forge repository named “dev_r9759_HPC09_ESIWACE”:

http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/nemo/svn/NEMO/branches/2018/dev_r9759_HPC09_ESIWACE

as done for BENCH 1.

Identification and determination of requirements for NEMO (see KPI 9.1: Progress in terms of retrieved defined requirements (metrics, features, etc.)) is to be accomplished and provided to the industrial HPC partners to provide HPC systems able to simulate high-resolution (coupled) models.

Concluding, thanks to the BENCH configuration, it has been possible to easily focus on MPI communication optimisation which is a work in progress. In addition, some kernel optimisations have been proposed during the presented optimisation phase that improve global performance of NEMO by about 9%.

Current and future work focuses on MPI datatype optimisation, shared MPI implementation and loop tiling.

Hybrid parallelisation

The Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) model is parallelised using a distributed memory approach implemented with MPI on the horizontal domain decomposition. A hybrid version of the NEMO code has been developed in the context of the ESIWACE project in order to understand if and how the model’s strong scalability can benefit from the combination of the shared memory paradigm with the distributed one.

Different implementations of the loop-based hybrid approach (implemented using OpenMP) were tested on representative NEMO kernels during the IS-ENES2 project⁹. The parallelisation of the outer loop (vertical levels) seemed to be the most promising, compared with loops merge and 3D tiling approaches.

As first step, during the ESIWACE project, the outer loop parallelisation (fine-grained) approach has been extended to the NEMO code v3.6 (Ocean physics, Sea-ice and Biogeochemistry) and tested on different HPC systems provided by the NEMO Consortium partners. The hybrid parallelisation has been evaluated on (i) a low-resolution configuration of the ocean component at 2° with Sea-ice (LIM2) and Biogeochemistry (TOP interface and PISCES model) and (ii) on the idealised GYRE configuration, configurable at different resolutions. Performance analysis has been done at routine level and on the whole code

⁹ I. Epicoco, S. Mocavero, A.R. Porter, S.M. Pickles, M. Ashworth, G. Aloisio, 2017, Hybridisation strategies and data structures for the NEMO ocean model, IJHPCA, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342016684930>

execution. The comparison between the hybrid version and the pure MPI one shows an improvement of ~20% and ~27% on the elapsed time for routines executing respectively MPI point-to-point and collective communications. The total execution time is reduced by ~5% when the strong scalability limit is reached. Results about this work have been presented at a [KNL Workshop](#)¹⁰. The code is available on a [CMCC GitHub repository](#) and can be accessed/downloaded (authorisation is needed).

As second step, a coarse-grained hybrid approach has been investigated. The aim was to limit the code modifications introduced by the second level of parallelism, making more transparent its maintenance for future developments. Moreover, the coarse-grained approach allowed us to increase the size of the OpenMP parallel regions as well as to reduce the synchronisation overhead. The approach has been discussed within the [NEMO HPC working group](#) and the [NEMO System Team](#) (login needed). The code has been evaluated on a representative NEMO kernel implementing the vertical physics, restructured to be compliant with the new approach. Standard and tiled coarse-grained implementations have been implemented and tested. Both versions show an improvement on the kernel execution time compared with the pure MPI version. In particular, at node level, the tiled version increases the parallel efficiency by ~13%, compared with both the MPI and the fine-grained version. The code is available in a [NEMO development branch](#). However the implementation of the coarse-grained parallel version requires a refactoring of the whole code. The impact of this change on the model development strategy is under evaluation within the NEMO Consortium.

The hybrid approach on NEMO will be also evaluated within a domain-specific language environment in the context of ESCAPE2 and ESiWACE2.

EC-Earth

Performance analysis of EC-Earth 3.2: Coupling

Earth system models include different components that can all run on different grid configurations, supporting a variety of spatial resolutions and time scales and exchanging boundary data with each other through a coupler. This process of coupling among components is not a trivial task and can be computationally expensive.

The main goal of this analysis is to study the computational cost that coupling represents for climate models using for this purpose EC-Earth as an example. The coupling between the two main components of EC-Earth, the ocean component (NEMO) and the atmospheric component (IFS) is evaluated, using OASIS3-MCT as coupler. The results show that the coupling could represent an important bottleneck (up to 50% of the time step of IFS) of the execution if a global conservation operation, combined to a large number of parallel processes and a high coupling frequency, is applied to the coupling fields without activating the optimisation options.

Two options available in OASIS3-MCT are evaluated to improve the coupling configuration. These options can reduce the coupling cost by more than 90%. The first one optimises the field exchanges between components and minimises the interpolation and communication process. The second one shows that OASIS3-MCT is able to reduce the MPI overhead by using global communications instead of one-to-all/all-to-one communications and by removing the serial calculations done by default on the master process. A reproducibility test

¹⁰ S. Mocavero, Towards KNL: the NEMO ocean model case study, KNL Workshop, 22-23 March 2017, CINECA, Italy

was done to evaluate the two optimisations. This test considers the chaotic nature of climate models and the small differences introduced by parallel operations (such as reduction operations). The test proves that the significant differences are less than 1%, comparing the simulation results of one-year experiments, using the default configuration and both optimisations (together and separately). Similar results are obtained when the results of two identical parallel simulations are compared. Additional tests have been done to evaluate the difficulty of load balancing the components of coupled models.

This work evaluates the computational performance of each component independently and studies how to achieve the best load balance among components by finding the optimal number of resources for each one.

All this analysis has been published as a BSC Technical Memorandum:

M.C. Acosta, X. Yepes-Arbós, S. Valcke, E. Maisonave, K. Serradell, O. Mula-Valls, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2016). Performance analysis of EC-Earth 3.2: Coupling. BSC-CES Technical Memorandum 2016-006

All code modifications related to this analysis have been reported to EC-Earth development portal in issue [#321](#) (login needed).

ICON

Improving I/O

The asynchronous I/O mechanism of ICON was tuned for a global 5km ICON setup, that was subsequently used for 40-day runs in the scope of the ESIWACE-supported initiative DYAMOND (DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains; international intercomparison project for global high-resolution simulations). In ICON, a number of dedicated I/O processes is defined via run scripts. These I/O processes can handle the output of one or more 2D or 3D fields. The optimal number of I/O processes is, however, problem-specific. For the 5km ICON-DYAMOND case, the number of I/O processes was investigated and finally set to 15. GRIB files were written, since they were significantly smaller than NetCDF files (even compared to compressed NetCDF data). Table 2 below shows the output time (wrt_output) as well as the total simulation time (total) in dependence from the number of available I/O processes and total number of compute nodes (each node running 12 MPI processes). More I/O processes were not found to be helpful since the new limiting factor was found to consist in the big 3D fields (which, at the time being, could not be further distributed on several I/O processes).

Table 2: Scalability of asynchronous I/O in ICON

Nodes	Number I/O procs	wrt_output (s)	total (s)
150	6	1091	7254
300	6	1332	4630
600	6	1661	3352
900	11	863	2532
900	15	749	1922

Improving global high-resolution model performance

In collaboration with BULL, the 5km ICON-DYAMOND setup was subsequently tuned with regard to compute performance on the supercomputer Mistral, partition compute2. Optimisations included loop re-orderings, improved compiler settings within the ICON model (in terms of preprocessor macros), and machine-specific configurations in the corresponding run scripts. This helped to improve the performance of the model significantly: on 600 compute nodes, the throughput rate could be lifted from initial 34 forecast days/compute day to 47 forecast days/day, corresponding to a 38% improvement.

ARM software for ICON use cases

ARM software solutions have been found particularly useful in ICON experiments for both profiling and for debugging. The latter included in particular debugging a checkpoint-restart issue in ICON.